

Development of Cheating Dilemma as a Thought Experiment in Assessing the Student's Ethical Decision Making

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Abstract

Thought experiments give each individual the opportunity to critically evaluate, examine their knowledge, and come up with the best possible solution while keeping in mind societal ethical norms and the implications of their actions. Given that students are continuously confronted with ethical decision-making throughout their studies, new thought experiments may be devised to assist them in assessing and improving their decision-making abilities. New Cheating Dilemmas have been constructed by taking into account numerous ideas such as utilitarianism, right-based theory, the doctrine of double effect, and employing components of the well-known thought experiments like the Trolley Problem and Fat-Man Problem. In this study, the Self-Cheating and Peer-Cheating dilemma tests were established to see if they provide the same chances for thought experiments to be employed in the academic integrity issue of cheating for students. Factors influencing college students' ethical decision-making in reaction to cheating have been explored. Various variants of the developed cheating problems were analyzed using the duty and consequentialist framework. The findings result in actions and policies that will be designed to improve awareness regarding the importance of academic integrity for students

Keywords: Academic Integrity, Cheating Issue, Behavioral Factors, College Students, Duty, Consequentialism

Introduction

In everyday scenarios, we are confronted with making decisions and selecting desired options that will serve as the best course of action for the situation that we experience (Edwards, 1954). The decision we make via evaluation and conclusion is influenced by our ability to recognize the problem and process the information through our ethical foundations. This foundation lays the groundwork for our understanding of rights, responsibilities, rewards, justice, and certain values. Our value system is profoundly rooted in ethics, which is inherent to who we are (Orme & Ashton, 2003).

Ethics is the foundation that is being built as we continue to choose between good and evil while taking into account the causes and effects on society's ideals and values. In every situation, one prerequisite for an acceptable decision is that it be ethical. Ethical

judgments promote well-being and do not hurt other persons affected by their actions. Some people make unethical judgments on purpose to benefit themselves, but even ethical decision-makers are occasionally presented with tough choices or ethical dilemmas. If an individual is allowed to put their decision-making skills to the test and is offered insights into a scenario, they may be able to enhance their decision-making abilities. Thought experiments are one example of such opportunities.

A thought experiment is a device that allows one to execute a deliberate, systematic process of intellectual reflection in order to guess about probable consequences for a specified antecedent within a certain issue area (Yeate, 2004). Over the last 40 years, thought experiments have played a significant role in many disputes in ethics, particularly applied ethics. Nonetheless, despite their widespread usage as a philosophical tool, there is something peculiar about the substantial dependence on thought experiments in fields of philosophy such as applied ethics, which are clearly geared toward practical life (Walsh 2011). One example of thought experiments that has been a popular topic is the trolley problem and its variants.

The trolley problem is an ethical thought experiment involving a fictitious scenario in which a spectator has the option of saving 5 individuals from being hit by a trolley by redirecting the trolley to kill only one person. Either decision – to sacrifice one person to rescue five, or to refrain from doing so – may be clearly understood and explained in the context of one of two well-known ethical theories: consequentialism and deontic ethics, respectively (Chelini et al., 2009). According to previous studies, up to 90% of people choose the utilitarian option of letting one person die in the trolley problem (Navarrete, McDonald, Mott, & Asher, 2012). As an alternative to utilitarianisms, philosophers believe in rights-based theory. Statements about people's fundamental rights, such as the right to life, liberty, expression, and property, as well as protection from oppression, unequal treatment, intolerance, and arbitrary invasion of privacy, provide the basic language and framework for ethical guidelines, according to the rights-based theory (Beauchamp & Childress, 2013). Other moral philosophers have proposed key rights-based ideas regarding the best method to prioritize competing duties that occur in situations like trolleys. In *The Theory of Morality* (1977), philosopher Donagan claimed that when selecting between obligations that may cause damage, one should choose the one that causes the least harm. This is referred to as "minimization of pain" by Popper (1966), and "negative utilitarianism" by Smart and Williams (1973). The doctrine of double effect is frequently mentioned in moral philosophers' responses to *The Trolley Problem*. Simply said, if doing something morally desirable has a morally horrible side consequence, it is ethically permitted if the bad side effect is unanticipated (Saemi, 2019). Even if the bad outcome was predicted, this is true. The Doctrine of Double Effect can be used to argue that the difference in moral permissibility in the trolley problem and its variants arises from the one being killed as a way of rescuing the five, but in *Bystander at the Switch*, the death of the

one is only a side effect of saving the five (Di Nucci, 2014).

The Trolley Problem has proven to be an effective heuristic and educational tool for bringing traditional ethical ideas to life by tying otherwise enigmatic concepts to concrete, foreseeable moral choices (Reamer, 2021). Students are nurtured and educated at educational institutions so that they are intellectually and ethically prepared for life. A student's life will be governed by the rules and regulations of the institution at many levels, beginning in the classroom and progressing to the departmental, college, and institutional levels. As a result, people are expected to observe an organization's rules and regulations even throughout their early careers for as long as they remain members of the organization. As a result, students and prospective professionals are expected to adhere to the standards established by their companies as early as their adolescence. They may meet situations that can be anticipated as an opportunity or a difficulty that will assist them determine whether to follow or stray from the standards. As a result of these opportunities and challenges, students will be able to exercise ethical decision-making and broaden their ethical viewpoints. Academic integrity is one of the most significant concepts and norms that students must follow throughout their academic careers.

Academic integrity gives students the flexibility to develop new ideas, knowledge, and creative works while respecting and recognizing the work of others. Students are expected to observe academic integrity norms throughout their education. Academic integrity is acting with responsibility, honesty, respect, trust, fairness, and bravery in any academic endeavor and avoiding any sort of cheating or dishonesty, even when the job is exceptionally challenging (International Center for Academic Integrity 2014).

Academic integrity in the educational setting might be defined as the habit of studying and carrying out academic work with fairness and coherence, striving to learn and being motivated by the service that this learning can bring others. However, there have been several interpretations of this notion (Fishman, 2016).

As of today, the majority of students have increasing access to technology and connectivity. Most students, without a proper understanding of the importance of academic integrity, see cheating, misuse of technology, and unpermitted collaborations as normal parts of their education (Dyer, 2010). This all leads to intentional or unintentional violations of academic policies that are based on societal ethical standards. Maintaining academic integrity would be difficult without thorough examination and knowledge of the concept. This research will aid in evaluating students' ethical decision making, notably in keeping their own academic integrity, through a series of modified thought experiments, primarily the trolley problem and its variation. Assessing the extent to which they would compromise their academic integrity can aid in the development of interventions and programs that would broaden their perspective on the value of academic integrity not just in their studies but also in their professional careers. This research aims to answer the following relevant research problems:

1. What are the factors affecting ethical decision making of college students in response to the academic integrity issue of cheating?
2. How can the Self-Cheating and Peer-Cheating Dilemma help the student decide in dealing with the academic integrity issue of cheating?
3. What interventions and policies shall be developed to raise awareness in the importance of keeping the academic integrity for the students?

Conceptual Framework

In the development of a thought experiment that resembles that of the Trolley Problem, it is important to look at the factors to consider why such an ethical dilemma is difficult to answer. The Trolley Problem has two courses of decision: one of the decisions is unethical and inflicts harm (letting five people die), while the other is still unethical but inflicts less harm (letting one person die). This makes the decision-making challenging because both decisions are unethical and inflict harm.

When using the trolley problem as a thought experiment in schools, students are faced with the dilemma of letting a trolley continue on a track and kill five people or pulling a lever and diverting the trolley to kill only one person when employing the trolley problem as a thought experiment in classrooms. This is especially true when the problem is compounded by additional circumstances. Because students are only beginning to develop the maturity necessary to make ethical decisions, it is critical that they have a trained sensitivity and practiced procedures for exploring ethical implications of each decision they make, especially if their academic integrity is at danger. When students practice it on a regular basis, the decision-making process approaches become so familiar in the form of availability heuristics that it automatically processes information for the students without the need for any reference or particular stages in the decision-making process. The more complex and novel the ethical judgments one must make, the more one must thoroughly investigate the issues, supported by insights and varied views.

Based on the theories relevant to the trolley problem: Theory of Utilitarianism, Rights-Based Approach, and the Doctrine of Double Effect, as well as the fundamental values of academic integrity and factors that affect the unethical academic behavior, it makes sense to suggest two broad frameworks to guide students' ethical decision making: The Consequentialist Framework and The Duty Framework.

There are two factors that distinguishes the consequentialist framework from the duty framework, these are: Actions and Outcomes. The key issue in the consequentialist framework's deliberative ethical decision-making process is "What type of outcomes should I aim to achieve," which focuses on all persons who will be directly or indirectly affected by an action's future impacts. While "What are my duties in this scenario, and what are the things I should never do?" is the key question in the duty framework's deliberative ethical decision-making process. It emphasizes on the need of paying attention

to the responsibilities that exist prior to the scenario and establishes obligations.

Using this factor, there can be a variety of thought experiments that includes the combination of ethical and unethical actions, and advantageous and disadvantageous outcomes. There are certain combinations that make the decision-making process difficult. In the case of the Trolley problem, both choice of action is unethical and disadvantageous, the only difference is that one outcome is observed as lesser disadvantageous.

Trolley problems and their modified variations are often used to help individuals improve their ethical decision-making in a heuristic way. A thought experiment shall be developed while taking into account Normative Ethical Theories: Utilitarianism, the Rights-based Approach, and the Doctrine of Double Effects, and the fundamental values of academic integrity and factors influencing unethical behaviors. In this study, the core concepts of academic integrity developed by the International Center for Academic Integrity will be used to create a thought experiment that resembles the trolley problems and link them to specific academic integrity challenge, which is cheating, to improve students' availability heuristics for effective ethical decision making.

The thought experiment for this study shall be known as “The Cheating Dilemma” with different variations. As cheating is the one action that violates all fundamental values of academic integrity and is often forced to be relied with when faced with factors affecting unethical academic behavior, it shall be the central choice of an unethical action along with its ethical counterpart, “studying”.

The students shall also be faced with the dichotomous outcomes of the advantageous and the disadvantageous situations. In analogy with the trolley problem, the people on the tracks which indicates the weight of the outcome shall become essential factors for the students such as academic subjects and their peers. In addition to the dilemmas created by the actions and outcomes, the prerequisite situations based on common occurrences also make decision making harder.

SELF-CHEATING DILEMMA. The exams in all of your subjects are quickly approaching. For some reason, you will fail unless you cheat on your exams. You can still study, but you can only do it for one subject that you will pass.

PEER-CHEATING DILEMMA. The exams in all of your subjects are quickly approaching, and your friends from other section are to fail. Your section is the first to take the exam, and informing your friends about the exam will help them all pass. If you do not inform them, you can focus on your own preparation and pass your exams.

In this Cheating Dilemma that involves examinations in five subjects, the student is faced with a choice of an unethical act of cheating or ethical act of studying, that will result into either the advantageous passing of five subjects or disadvantageous failure of the four subjects while only passing one subject. This variation is the combination of ethical and unethical, and advantageous and disadvantageous. There are also other variations to be considered summarized in the table below:

Table 1: Summary of decision variation based on actions and outcomes

Course of Actions	First Outcome Combination	Second Outcome Combination	Third Outcome Combination	Fourth Outcome Combination
Both Ethical	Both Advantageous	Both Disadvantageous	Advantageous and Disadvantageous	
Both Unethical	Both Advantageous	Both Disadvantageous	Advantageous and Disadvantageous	
Ethical and Unethical	Both Advantageous	Both Disadvantageous	Advantageous and Disadvantageous	Disadvantageous and Advantageous
Unethical and Ethical	Both Advantageous	Both Disadvantageous	Advantageous	Disadvantageous

Using all the combinations of actions and outcomes, there are 11 developed variations for the self-cheating dilemma shown in the table below.

Table 2: Self-Cheating dilemma decision combinations

Variation	Action	Outcome	Course of Action with Respective Outcome in terms of Academic Subjects
1	Ethical	Advantage	Studying all subjects and passing all subjects
	Ethical	Advantage	Studying one subject and passing one subject
2	Ethical	Disadvantage	Studying all subjects and failing all subjects
	Ethical	Disadvantage	Studying one subject and failing one subject
3	Ethical	Advantage	Studying all subjects and passing all subjects
	Ethical	Disadvantage	Studying all subjects and failing all subjects
4	Unethical	Advantage	Cheating all subjects and passing all subjects
	Unethical	Advantage	Cheating one subject and passing one subject
5	Unethical	Disadvantage	Cheating all subjects and failing all subjects

	Unethical	Disadvantage	Cheating one subject and failing one subject
6	Unethical	Advantage	Cheating all subjects and passing all subjects
	Unethical	Disadvantage	Cheating all subjects and failing all subjects
7	Ethical	Advantage	Studying all subjects and passing all subjects
	Unethical	Advantage	Cheating one subjects and passing one subjects
8	Ethical	Disadvantage	Studying all subjects and failing all subjects
	Unethical	Disadvantage	Cheating one subject and failing one subject
9	Ethical	Advantage	Studying all subjects and passing all subjects
	Unethical	Disadvantage	Cheating all subjects and failing all subjects
10	Ethical	Disadvantage	Studying all subjects and failing all subjects
	Unethical	Advantage	Cheating all subjects and passing all subjects
11	Unethical	Advantage	Cheating all subjects and passing all subjects
	Ethical	Advantage	Studying one subject and passing one subject
12	Unethical	Disadvantage	Cheating all subjects and failing all subjects
	Ethical	Disadvantage	Studying one subject and failing one subject

For the peer-cheating dilemma, there are 11 developed variations using the given combinations and outcomes.

Table 3: Peer-Cheating dilemma decision combinations

Variation	Action	Outcome	Course of Action with Respective Outcome in terms of Peer
1	Ethical	Advantage	Studying with friends, friends pass but you fail
	Ethical	Advantage	Studying with yourself, friends pass but you fail
2	Ethical	Disadvantage	Studying with friends, friends fail but you pass

	Ethical	Disadvantage	Studying with yourself, friends fail but you pass
3	Ethical	Advantage	Studying with friends, friends pass but you fail
	Ethical	Disadvantage	Studying with friends, friends fail but you pass
4	Unethical	Advantage	Cheating with friends, friends pass but you fail
	Unethical	Advantage	Cheating with yourself, friends pass but you fail
5	Unethical	Disadvantage	Cheating with friends, friends fail but you pass
	Unethical	Disadvantage	Cheating with yourself, friends fail but you pass
6	Unethical	Advantage	Cheating with friends, friends pass but you fail
	Unethical	Disadvantage	Cheating with friends, friends fail but you pass
7	Ethical	Advantage	Studying with friends, friends pass but you fail
	Unethical	Advantage	Cheating with yourself, friends pass but you fail
8	Ethical	Disadvantage	Studying with friends, friends fail but you pass
	Unethical	Disadvantage	Cheating with yourself, friends fail but you pass
9	Ethical	Advantage	Studying with friends, friends pass but you fail
	Unethical	Disadvantage	Cheating with friends, friends fail but you pass
10	Ethical	Disadvantage	Passing with friends, friends fail but you pass
	Unethical	Advantage	Cheating with friends, friends pass but you fail
11	Unethical	Advantage	Cheating with friends, friends pass but you fail
	Ethical	Advantage	Studying with yourself, friends pass but you fail
12	Unethical	Disadvantage	Cheating with friends, friends fail but you pass
	Ethical	Disadvantage	Studying with yourself, friends fail but you pass

All the variations of the cheating dilemma shall be seen into two perspectives, using a research paradigm that incorporates the consequentialist and the duty framework.

Figure 1: The consequentialist framework for the cheating dilemma

In this paradigm, students will be confronted with several varieties of the cheating dilemma, each with its own set of actions, results, and scenarios. The consequentialist paradigm holds that people focus on the results of their decisions rather than the activities they do, and that "the goal justifies the means." Individual decisions are influenced by terminal values, which comprise desired and states of outcomes, as observed in normative ethical theories. These include utilitarianism, which focuses on what is good for the greatest number of people, rights-based theory, which dictates what is the end that fulfills the greatest number of people's rights, and the doctrine of double effects, which demonstrates the outcome of the greater good regardless of the other consequences. Because the individual is more focused on the outcome, it is only after they make the decision that they recognize what they have done may be ethical or unethical.

Figure 2: The duty framework for the cheating dilemma

Looking at the other side of the paradigm of duty framework, students will be confronted with several varieties of the cheating dilemma, each with its own set of actions, results, and scenarios. The duty framework focuses individuals on the tasks they must fulfill as part of their duties, such as academic integrity in the case of students. Individual decisions are influenced by instrumental values, which include objectives and states of conduct as observed in normative ethical theories, basic ideals of academic integrity, and causes influencing unethical academic activity. Part of the student's obligation is to follow each core principle of academic integrity; nevertheless, certain circumstances require them to diverge from their duties, as demonstrated in the causes influencing unethical academic behavior. When an individual takes a choice, it is only after they have made it that they understand what they have done may be advantageous or disadvantageous since they are more focused on the acts that they must carry out as part of their tasks.

Materials and Methods

The data analysis technique used in this study is guided by the research design and conceptual framework. Demographic Information, Factors Affecting Behavior, and Cheating Dilemmas are the three sections of the questionnaire. The descriptive statistics will be used to analyze each part. In this study, descriptive statistics were employed to define the basic characteristics of the data and information acquired through the survey. Simple summaries of the college students' responses to the various questions should be supplied. Together with rudimentary graphical analysis, they provide the foundation of almost every quantitative data analysis.

The data analysis for the final segment of the data will be done using a combination of descriptive statistics and the conceptual framework technique. In terms of the conceptual framework, both the duty and consequentialist frameworks will be used to determine if college students made decisions based on their duty to maintain academic integrity or on the number of beneficiaries in each decision. The summary of findings and conclusion will provide insights on the overall patterns and causal links in the responses that have been acquired after describing, charting, quantifying, and analyzing data in each question. This information will be used to make recommendations.

Results and Discussion

Table 4: The duty framework for the cheating dilemma summary of decision variation based on actions and outcomes

Factors Affecting Behavior	Frequency/Weighted Average
Pressure to Get Excellent Grades	Self (47.2%) Family and Relatives (30.6%) Teachers (17.95%) Friends (3.1%) Classmates (1.3%)
Environment (Cheating)	Classmates (47.2%) Friends (25.6%) Self (23.3%) Family and Relatives (2.2%) Teachers (1.7%)
Intelligence Level	Very Good (44.3%) Good (30%) Fair (9.9%) Excellent (9.5%) Passing (6.3%)
Fundamental Values of Academic Integrity	Respect (95.23%) Responsibility (94.78%) Trust (94.31%) Courage (93.75%) Honesty (93.44%) Fairness (92.09%)
Most acceptable cheating behavior	Actively try to prevent other students from doing well (32.96%) Lie to a professor about the reason for overdue work or absence from class (29.49%) Blindly answer a questionnaire without any thought (27.35%) Send test answers in group messages (26.96%) Copy and paste material from the Internet directly into an assignment without attribution (26.80) Peek for answer during the test (26.40%) Ask test answers in group messages (25.93%)
Trolley Problem Moral Dilemma	Let one person die (77.1%) Let five individual die (22.9%)
Fat-Man Problem Moral Dilemma	Push the stranger off the bridge (63.6%) Let five individual die (36.4%)

According to Barnett and Dalton (1981), six elements influence students' behavior:

academic pressure, the environment, cognitive levels, personality, misunderstanding the concept of cheating, and moral judgment.

The biggest source of pressure in achieving good marks has been found as one's own. Understanding the origins of academic pressure can aid in the development of interventions that will reduce the stress felt by students. Because of the pressure they are under, it also leads pupils to do immoral decisions in order to earn good scores. According to the responses, the respondents' peers are the primary source of the respondents' cheating activities and surroundings. Students' academic performance suffers as a result of the cheating environment. If students see cheating as a common occurrence in their environment, they may be encouraged to do it as well. Understanding the probable origins of a cheating environment aids in the development of viable treatments to reduce the student's exposure to a cheating environment.

Academic integrity essential principles are the core values that students must possess in order to retain academic integrity and avoid unethical behavior. According to the responses, respect is the most important value, although other values are nearly equally significant. The awareness of students in engaging in various unethical academic activities is the next element to consider. Students' most acceptable conduct is to hinder their peers from achieving better, while their least acceptable behavior is to ask exam answers in group messaging. Assessing students' comprehension of these unethical academic activities can assist instructors inform and educate students about the necessity of not engaging in these unethical academic behaviors.

Students' level of intelligence has been determined to be very good, not the top but still above average. However, this is merely a self-evaluation, and students' true Intelligence levels may differ. Understanding the students' present intelligence level can still assist design interventions for their ethical decision making, as students who consider themselves as capable are more likely to engage in academic integrity-preserving activity. Finally, moral judgments have an impact on ethical conduct. Understanding how the students' moral standards function can provide the researcher with information into the students' most likely conclusion in the self-cheating and peer-cheating dilemma. As most students are perceived to choose the decision that will cause the least harm or the greatest benefit, the researcher wishes to test whether this is still the case when the students are faced with varying decisions and combinations of ethical and unethical with advantages and disadvantages that affect the student's subjects and friends.

Understanding all of these factors are essential foundation for the establishment of specific policies, programs and interventions that the institution can create to raise awareness and addressing the academic integrity issue of cheating.

Table 5: Self-Cheating dilemma summary of decision variation based on actions and outcomes

Self-Cheating Dilemma			
Variation	1 st Option	2 nd Option	Observation for Majority of Respondents
Original	21.3%	78.7%	Duty is Greater than Consequence
V.1	96%	4%	Duty is Achieved; Consequentialism is Achieved
V.2	26.9%	73.1%	Duty is Achieved; Consequentialism is Achieved
V.3	97.6%	2.4%	Duty is Achieved; Consequentialism is Achieved
V.4	39.1%	60.9%	Duty is Compromised; Consequentialism is Compromised
V.5	11.9%	88.1%	Duty is Compromised; Consequentialism is Achieved
V.6	97%	3%	Duty is Compromised; Consequentialism is Compromised
V.7	95.7%	4.3%	Duty is Achieved; Consequentialism is Achieved
V.8	53.8%	46.2%	Duty is Achieved; Consequentialism is Compromised
V.9	96.8%	3.2%	Duty is Achieved; Consequentialism is Achieved
V.10	68%	32%	Duty is Achieved; Consequentialism is Compromised
V.11	20.6%	79.4%	Duty is Achieved; Consequentialism is Compromised
V.12	8.3%	91.7%	Duty is Achieved; Consequentialism is Compromised

The purpose of the self-cheating dilemma is to put students' ethical decision-making skills to the test when confronted with diverse combinations of ethical and unethical activities, as well as favorable and unfavorable results. The original cheating dilemma demonstrates that the majority of students performed their duties rather of selecting the outcome that would benefit their subjects the greatest.

Overall, it can be noted that when students are presented with both ethical behaviors and different results, they will pick the outcome that provides the most benefit while causing the least harm to their subjects. When given the choice between unethical

activities and different results, the majority of students will select the less unethical alternative. When presented with a choice between ethical and unethical decisions with varied results, the majority of students will opt to be ethical and fulfill their responsibilities.

Table 6: Peer-Cheating dilemma summary of decision variation based on actions and outcomes

Peer-Cheating Dilemma			
Variation	1 st Option	2 nd Option	Observation for Majority of Respondents
Original	13%	87%	Duty is Greater than Consequence
V.1	45.1%	54.9%	Duty is Achieved; Consequentialism is Achieved Action is done alone
V.2	43.5%	56.5%	Duty is Achieved; Consequentialism is Compromised Action is done alone
V.3	31.2%	68.8%	Duty is Achieved; Consequentialism is Compromised Action is done with others
V.4	42.7%	57.3%	Duty is Compromised; Consequentialism is Achieved Action is done alone
V.5	40.3%	59.7%	Duty is Compromised; Consequentialism is Compromised Action is done alone
V.6	42.7%	57.3%	Duty is Compromised; Consequentialism is Compromised Action is done with others
V.7	69.6%	30.4%	Duty is Achieved; Consequentialism is Achieved Action is done with others
V.8	79.1%	20.9%	Duty is Achieved; Consequentialism is Compromised Action is done with others
V.9	74.3%	25.7%	Duty is Achieved; Consequentialism is Achieved Action is done with others
V.10	88.9%	11.1%	Duty is Achieved; Consequentialism is Compromised Action is done with others
V.11	18.6%	81.4%	Duty is Achieved; Consequentialism is Achieved Action is done alone

V.12	17.4%	82.6%	Duty is Achieved; Consequentialism is Compromised Action is done alone
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In parallel to the Self-Cheating Dilemma, the versions of the Peer-Cheating dilemma have tested and proven that students will continue to do their duties even if their peers are in risk of failing a grade. According to the students, one's grade is one's duty, and only one's actions can justify the outcomes that they will receive. Students have maintained their obligation to be academically ethical, but it is also emphasized that students prefer to work or behave alone rather than with their friends.

But how can all of these variations on the self-cheating and peer-cheating dilemma benefit the students? As we all know, there are cases offered that are plausible and situations that have clear solutions to the dilemma. The purpose of thought experiments is to put an individual's ethical considerations, including values, to the test. The students have confronted a variety of actions and outcomes in the given situations, and all of these challenges, no matter how difficult or easy the questions are, allow the students to measure gains and analyze acts that they believe are proper, correct, or up to their personal and societal standards. There is a lot to think about, including the factors influencing behavior, and it helps to understand where the responses are coming from. The thought experiments personally helps the students to be more critical in thinking before making decisions. By carefully weighting the actions and assessing the consequences while considering the institutional policies and society's ethical standards.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the responses to the Self-Cheating and Peer-Cheating dilemmas are influenced by the student's point of view, experience, surroundings, ability, and academic integrity. The students rate themselves as capable and very good in their studies, and based on their replies, they do not allow their personal pressure to get high marks to compromise their academic integrity. Despite the possibility of failure in their own subject or in the subject of a friend.

Students feel that the most important values they must practice in their academics are respect, responsibility, and trust. Respecting the current regulations on academic behavior, accepting responsibility for acting ethically, and retaining the trust that has been placed in them to make the right option in order to maintain their academic integrity. With these values, most students consider actions such as requesting and peeking for answers, as well as plagiarism, to be inappropriate.

Students' perspectives on moral dilemmas such as the trolley problem and the fat-mat problem support consequentialism because both dilemmas involve the unethical action of killing one or five people. In the academic perspective, Self-Cheating and Peer-Cheating

Dilemmas alter these notions of being offered the choice of acting ethically or unethically while considering the ideas of consequentialism. According to the responses, it is preferable to study rather than cheat, even if it means failing all subjects or all of the respondent's friends. In certain cases, students will only cheat if they have no other alternative; nevertheless, if they can study, regardless of the outcome, the majority will choose to keep their academic integrity. Duties have been prioritized over the consequences that benefit all subjects or all of their friends.

The overall response for the dilemma shows willingness from the students to act ethically and study for their examinations, provided that they have the choice. The institution can help improve this behavior in the following ways:

Administration. The Administration is the central body in charge of developing policies for the institutions. And, through programs and written policies created to address issues of academic integrity, these policies should be properly explained to students and educators. When cheating events occur, the administration should have rules and regulations in place for resolving issues and adopting a legal framework.

Educators. The educators have the most engagement with the students. They can assist students by disseminating academic policies about the preservation of obligations and responsibilities. Furthermore, educators can help address the factors influencing behavior by encouraging students and decreasing pressure to achieve high grades, properly designing assessments and activities for students to avoid cheating with their classmates, and improving students' capabilities so that they can work independently.

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